

SOCIAL MOBILITY AS THE KEY FACTOR FOR HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT

Khaydarova Malika

Lecturer at the Department of Economics at Karshi State University

Musurmonova Mahbuba

Lecturer at the Department of Economics at Karshi State University

Annotation.

Relevance and goals.

The article reveals the concepts of "social mobility", "social lift" and their impact on the development and modernization of Uzbek society. The quality of human capital is considered, namely, the human capacity for mobility in society, which leads to economic prosperity and faster social progress. The relationship between the institution of higher education and social mobility is considered. Higher education serves as a tool for successful employment, career advancement, and self-improvement. The importance of social mobility for the development and modernization of Uzbek society, which is aimed at developing the individual, providing him with opportunities for professional and career growth.

The purpose of the work is to analyze the state of social mobility in modern Uzbek society and present the implementation of the work of the social elevator.

Materials and methods.

The implementation of the tasks was carried out on the basis of a structural-functional approach, analysis and generalization of statistical data, scientific analysis of a wide range of sources, including scientific and periodical literature.

Results.

In the course of the analysis, it was revealed that social mobility is an important component of the life of society. The modernization tasks set by the state can be successfully implemented only with the solution

problems of social mobility of the younger generation. From socially active youth, from the personal success of each, the processes of development and modernization. Such a mechanism can and should be a social elevator, operating nationwide.

Conclusions.

Exploring social mobility as a factor in the development and modernization of Russian society, we can conclude that each member society has a fair chance to realize its potential and for this various projects and programs are needed.

Key words: *social lift, social mobility, human capital, social development, social status.*

Today, the term "modernization" has firmly entered and entrenched itself in public, journalistic and scientific discourses. Modernization needed for the progressive development of Uzbekistan, to increase its competitiveness in the world market. Modernization development will allow to outline optimal strategic scenarios and will connect various spheres of society's life with each other. The solution of such problems is possible only in a country that is ready to self-development, qualitative growth and innovation. Systematic social and technical modernization is not possible without "knowledge economy", without improving the quality of human capital, without directing the development of national intelligence to an innovative direction. Many researchers agree that not only the size, but also the quality of human capital (health, knowledge, mobility) in the post-industrial era becomes the leading factor in the sustainable development of society.

It is from the quality of human capital, which includes its health, knowledge, the ability to be mobile, depend on the processes of modernization. In terms of self-

organization, Uzbek society is unique. At the core self-organization lies personal economic interest. Those issues that the elite puts on the agenda for society turn out to be of no interest to Uzbek society. The reason for this is the presence of the Uzbek elite and civil society in completely different social spaces. The majority of our citizens have different life strategies from the elite. Uzbek people have little idea about recruiting into the elite. Ignorance of the foundations of our social life hinders the modernization and progressive development of our society and state.

Social lift is a certain channel, mechanism or way of changing the social status of a person. A way that will help you take a more prestigious position or, conversely, a lower one. Most members of our society form social and economic strategies for themselves. It is extremely difficult to achieve success in many areas of public life, and even more so to make a good career, taking into account our modern Uzbek realities. All these difficulties can lead to apathy and distrust in society.

Promotion occurs by changing statuses, roles and due to certain objective social conditions. social lift in this area implies career growth, the reasons for which are the constantly increasing level of professional competence, achieving status goals by satisfying a need in achieving success and professional self-realization, using the possibilities of the achieved status for the effective implementation of professional activities [3].

If there are sufficiently high-quality social elevators, then each of its members is sure that, under certain conditions, he can achieve the desired result [4].

The term "social mobility" was formed in 1927 by the American sociologist of Russian origin P. Sorokin. According to his concept, there are two types of social mobility: horizontal and vertical. Horizontal mobility is movement at the same level of social stratification, without the individual changing his socially significant positions. Another thing is vertical mobility, which involves the movement of an individual from one layer in the other in the social hierarchy both upwards (upward mobility) and down (descending). Modern society is distinguished by the fact that both individual social actors and social groups freely change their social position and social status regardless

of their starting position. P. Sorokin states: “Mobility contributes to economic prosperity and faster social progress. Since in a mobile society individuals are better distributed across social strata, they are probably more successful in their duties than those who are less well-placed individuals in an immobile society. Thanks to these and to some other factors, a mobile society progresses more intensively than an immobile one. This position is confirmed by history. We have already pointed out the fact that periods of intense mobility, as a rule, were accompanied by significant progress in the sphere of spiritual life. As for economic prosperity, as V. Pareto established, between periods marked by intensive mobility and an increase in economic well-being there is a direct relationship” [5, p. 492].

The issues of social mobility are devoted to many Russian studies that consider objective and subjective aspects. This topic was addressed by such researchers as Z. T. Golenkova [6], M. K. Gorshkov [7], V. V. Semenova [8], P. E. Sushko [9], N. E. Tikhonova [10] and others.

The social lift is characterized by constancy, regularity of work and the presence of game rules that ensure vertical mobility. That is, there should be a system of legal norms and procedures that allowed to perform for some social institution the function of a social elevator. In this case, society becomes more open, and social the well-being of citizens is improving. If the society does not provide vertical mobility of citizens, then, as a result, there may be indifference to the elections, waves of protest, the emergence of radical groups and opposition sentiments, and aggravation of interethnic relations. The combination of a high level of inequality with low social mobility in society will lead to the fact that a social group located at the bottom of the social ladder, will not be able to navigate freely and comfortably in social relations. In the socio-economic life of modern society, an idle social elevator will sooner or later lead to stagnation in labor productivity, a low level of innovation, depression and lack of activity of young people. Normal personnel movement in the civil service is hampered by the fact that Everyone tries to be leaders, not good specialists. In business, the opposite problem is observed - self-employed, so as well as for individual

entrepreneurs, it is unprofitable to switch to medium-sized businesses, in this case the number of inspections and claims immediately increases, and at the same time, the percentage of risk increases [11].

In addition, social lifts are no longer a rigidly structured reality. Development of the information society and access to a large amount of various information makes it possible for a person to design his own future on his own. In such a case, a person there is a "lucky chance" to be the master of one's own destiny. It is commonly believed that moving up requires talent, intelligence, skill, resourcefulness, hard work, perseverance, risk-taking, and correct strategy. An example is M. E. Zuckerberg, one of the developers and founders of the social network Facebook. In January In 2018, he was the fifth in the Forbes magazine list and the youngest multibillionaire with a fortune of \$ 70 billion. The emergence and development of digital technologies has led to the formation new social elevator - is digital. Today the Internet and social networks are tools to promote yourself or your services without large material investments. The digital elite are those who collect many (millions) of likes [14]. Student youth are in particular need of social lifts. Students are a fairly large part of today's youth and urban population. Students are advanced, most educated and trained part of the youth, which undoubtedly allows them to be put on the first plan and include among the progressive and advanced groups of youth [15]. As a student and receiving higher education, a person strives realize your dream. Most students are aware that a higher education institution is one of the means of social development and growth of young people in various directions, and this is a prerequisite for social advancement. The specifics of studying at a university is another important feature that allows you to expand the scope of communication. An analysis of global trends in the development of the institution of education shows that its potential as a social lift is gradually being lost. On the need to identify possible risks in the labor market, depending on level of education sociologists warn [16]. It's getting harder for youth who received a diploma of graduation from a higher educational institution, move up the social ladder [17]. Over

the past nine years, Uzbeks more often began to consider higher education a necessity - the share of supporters of the opinion that a diploma about higher education should be received, because it is accepted (from 6% in 2010 to up to 18% in 2019). Most often this is said by young people aged from 18 to 24 years old (25%). Among them, the most common is the practice of obtaining higher education in order to improve social status (18% versus a share of 13% among all respondents) [18]. In general, the majority of Uzbeks are confident that higher education accompanies a successful career and makes it easier to achieve life goals (76% in 2008 and 58% in 2019). All this indicates that society is more critical of the importance of higher education and it is one of the tools to success in life. It is not easy to set social elevators in motion, we need completely new programs for promoting personnel, especially talented youth [19], who, in turn, should understand that the main quality in the modern labor market is competitiveness [20]. The social lift gives a chance to realize personal and business potential, take a worthy social position and achieve success in your career. The work of the social elevator contributes to the independence of a person for country due to their own perseverance, determination, strong character and all leadership abilities. This is especially true for young people, for which the social lift may well become a springboard to the "other life". Thanks to such social lifts, people occupy a higher position in society, turn into influential politicians, scientists, businessmen, experts, etc. In modern conditions, the social elevator should become the basis for the consolidation of constructive, creative socio-economic, political forces, the formation and development of which will take place from the bottom up. As an example, we can recall the Soviet cities in which new industries and new technologies developed, and these settlements themselves were often rebuilt a new place gave more opportunities for self-realization. The intensity of the formation of modernization processes will depend on from socially active youth, from launching an effective mechanism to support each young person to achieve personal and common success. Such a mechanism can and should be a social elevator, operating nationwide. Reaching higher levels social mobility should be perceived as a major political goal, it requires the

formation of a holistic strategy at the state level with the definition of appropriate key performance indicators to address a wide range of problems.

REFERENCES

1. Becker G. S. Human Capital. Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education. New York; London: Columbia University Press, 1964, 187 p.
2. Bychenko Yu. G., Loginova L. V. Izvestiya Saratovskogo universiteta. Novaya seriya. Ser.: Sotsiologiya. Politologiya [Proceedings of Saratov University. New series. Series: Sociology. Politology]. 2008, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 47–54. [In Russian]
3. Alekhin E. V., Boyarova E. A. Obshchestvo: sotsiologiya, psikhologiya, pedagogika [Society: sociology, psychology, pedagogy]. 2019, no. 7 (63), pp. 27–32. [In Russian]
4. Sorokin P. A. Monitoring obshchestvennogo mneniya: ekonomicheskie i sotsial'nye peremeny [Public opinion monitoring: economic and social change]. 2004, no. 2 (70), pp. 101–110. [In Russian]
5. Sorokin P. A. Sotsial'naya mobil'nost' [Social mobility]; transl. from Engl. M. V. Sokolova. Moscow: Academia: LVS, 2005, 588 p. [In Russian]
6. Golenkova Z. T., Sushko P. E. Sotsiologicheskie issledovaniya [Sociological researches]. 2016, no. 12, pp. 95–104. [In Russian]
7. Gorshkov M. K. Vestnik Rossiyskoy akademii nauk [Bulletin of the Russian Academy of Sciences]. 2020, vol. 90, no. 3, pp. 232–242. [In Russian]
8. Begemann B., Van'ke A. V., Golenkova Z. T., Epikhina Yu. B., Kolennikova N. D., Petrovich Ya., Polukhina E. V., Rozhdestvenskaya E. Yu., Semenova V. V., Strel'nikova A. V., Sushko P. E., Tartakovskaya I. N., Cherkashina T. Yu., Chernysh M. F., Shuvakovich U., Yaroshenko S. S. Sotsial'naya mobil'nost' v uslozhnyayushchetsya obshchestve: ob"ektivnye i sub"ektivnye aspekty: monografiya [Social mobility in an increasingly complex society: objectival and subjective aspects: monograph]. Moscow: FNISTs RAN, 2019, 512 p. [In Russian]

9. Sushko P. E. Teoriya i praktika obshchestvennogo razvitiya [Theory and practice of social development]. 2018, no. 2 (120), pp. 8–12. [In Russian]
10. Tikhonova N. E. Vestnik Instituta sotsiologii [Bulletin of the Institute of Sociology]. 2017, no. 21, pp. 140–165. [In Russian]
11. Il'in P. A., Kandakova N. S. Yunyy uchenyy [Young scientist]. 2020, no. 4 (34), pp. 47–49. Available at: <https://moluch.ru/young/archive/34/1992/> (accessed 20.10.2020). [In Russian]
12. Federal'naya sluzhba gosudarstvennoy statistiki [Federal State Statistics Service]. Available at: www.stat.uz
13. Programma vyyavleniya i podderzhki talantlivoy molodezhi v oblasti predprinimatel'stva i menedzhmenta «Sotsial'nyy lift» [The program for identifying and supporting talented youth in the field of entrepreneurship and management “Social Lift”]. Social lift. Available at: <http://www.soclift.ru/index.htm> (accessed 20.09.2020). [In Russian]
14. Sotsial'nye lify: ponyatie i osnovnye vidy [Social lifts: concept and main types]. Mentamore. Available at: <https://mentamore.com/socium/socialnye-lify.html> (accessed 20.09.2020). [In Russian]
15. Sitarov V., Shutenko A., Shutenko E. AlmaMater. 2007, no. 7, pp. 13–18. [In Russian]
16. Golenkova Z. T., Kosharnaya G. B., Kosharnyy V. P. Integratsiya obrazovaniya [Integration of education]. 2018, vol. 22, no. 2 (91), pp. 262–273. [In Russian]
17. Svad'bina T. B., Nemova O. A. Vestnik Surgutskogo gosudarstvennogo pedagogicheskogo universiteta [Bulletin of Surgut State Pedagogical University]. 2018, no. 2 (53), pp. 111–118. [In Russian]
18. Dannye oprosov. Vysshee obrazovanie: sotsial'nyy lift ili poteryannoe vremya? [Survey data. Higher education: social lift or wasted time?]. VTsIOM. Available at: <https://wciom.ru/index.php?id=236&uid=9808> (accessed 15.09.2020). [In Russian]

19. Sotsial'noe samochuvstvie naseleniya v usloviyakh reform: regional'nyy aspekt [Social state of health of the population in the context of reforms: regional aspect]. Ed. by M. K. Gorshkov. Moscow; Saint-Petersburg: Nestor-Istoriya, 2011, 176 p. [In Russian]

20. Korzh N. V., Karimova L. F. Nauka. Obshchestvo. Gosudarstvo [Science. Society. State]. 2017, vol. 5, no. 1 (17), pp. 155–161. Available at: <http://esj.pnzgu.ru> (accessed 20.09.2020). [In Russian]

21. ИНСОН КАПИТАЛИНИ ШАКЛЛАНИШИ, РИВОЖЛАНИШИ ДАРАЖАЛАРИ ВА ИНСОН КАПИТАЛИНИ ИНВЕСТИЦИЯЛАШ ГП Эркаева, СЗ Рузикулов *Gospodarka i Innowacje*. 24, 225-229

21. LABOR MOTIVATION IN SMALL BUSINESS ENTERPRISES KG Fayzullaevich, EG Panjiyevna, FK Gaybulla o'g'li *American Journal of Economics and Business Management* 4 (2), 89-93